

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new lactosylated-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides)

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Abstract : Several 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino and 4-phenyl-5-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides and *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and 1-aryl-3-phenyl thiocarbamides with *N*-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride respectively. The structure of these new *N*-lactosylated-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrochlorides have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral analysis. Antimicrobial activities of these compounds were evaluated.

Keywords : Thiocarbamides, isothiocarbamoyl chloride, 1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrochlorides.

Introduction

Chemistry of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride with special utility in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing five and six membered heterocyclic compounds has been exhaustively investigated by number of chemists¹⁻³. Very few compounds containing thioamido group and having lactosyl substituent on nitrogen have been reported and tested for their biological activity⁴⁻⁶. In view of our interest in the synthesis of newer types of 1,2,4-dithiazolidines, we report herein the simple method for the synthesis of 1,2,4-dithiazolidines by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride⁷ and 1-aryl-3-phenyl thiocarbamides with *N*-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride. The required 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides have been obtained by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate with several aryl amines.

Results and discussion

Several 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides) have been prepared by the condensation of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1) and *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) in CHCl₃ similarly

the interaction of *N*-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (4) and aryl thiocarbamides (5) was carried out in CHCl₃ medium, evolution of HCl was noticed. After condensation the solvent was distilled off and the resulting syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60-80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (3a-g) (Scheme 1) (Table 1) and (6a-g) (Scheme 2) (Table 2) respectively. The products were purified by chloroform-petroleum ether.

The structure of the products were confirmed by spectral analysis (IR⁸, NMR⁹ and Mass¹⁰). The specific rotation of the products were also recorded¹¹. All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Experimental

Specific rotations were measured on Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter at 28 °C in CHCl₃. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR spectrophotometer (4000-450 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol-SX-102 (FAB) instrument.

*Synthesis of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1a-g) :*

A mixture of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-tolyl, (c) *o*-tolyl, (d) *m*-tolyl, (e) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (f) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (g) *m*-Cl-phenyl

Scheme 1

Table 1. 3-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides) (3a-g) (Scheme 1)

Reactants : (I) 1-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1a-g), (II) phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) (0.005 M 15 ml CHCl_3)

Product	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Requires)		$[\alpha]_D^{28}$ (c, 0.156 CHCl_3)
			N	S	
3a	132–135	80	3.12 (3.14)	4.60 (4.78)	+113 $^{\circ}$
3b	155–158	82	3.12 (3.10)	4.40 (4.73)	+95 $^{\circ}$
3c	145–148	86	3.11 (3.10)	4.61 (4.73)	+130 $^{\circ}$
3d	140	85	3.06 (3.10)	4.55 (4.73)	+105 $^{\circ}$
3e	146–148	90	3.01 (3.06)	4.17 (4.66)	+118 $^{\circ}$
3f	110	87	2.99 (3.06)	4.47 (4.66)	+98 $^{\circ}$
3g	147	89	3.09 (3.06)	4.58 (4.66)	+110 $^{\circ}$

Satisfactory C and H analysis were found in all cases.

where R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Scheme 2

Table 2. 4-Phenyl-5-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrochloride (6a-g) (Scheme 2)

Reactants : (a) *N*-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.0025 *M*, 1.86 g),
(b) 1-aryl-3-phenyl thiocarbamides (0.0025 *M*)

Sl. no.	Aryl thiocarbamides	g	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	[α] ²⁸ _D (c, CHCl ₃)	R _f	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
								N	S
1.	1,3-Diphenyl	0.57	6a	88.51	122–126	+394.8	0.63	4.25 (4.30)	6.59 (6.55)
2.	1- <i>o</i> -Cl-Phenyl-3-	0.65	6b	90.83	118–122	+306.02	0.49	4.11 (4.15)	6.30 (6.33)
3.	1- <i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl-3-	0.65	6c	89.64	115–118	+207.30	0.54	4.09 (4.15)	6.36 (6.33)
4.	1- <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl-3-	0.65	6d	77.29	115–120	+334.3	0.96	4.11 (4.15)	6.37 (6.33)
5.	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl-3-	0.60	6e	62.19	110–115	+256.6	0.45	4.20 (4.24)	6.44 (6.46)
6.	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-3-	0.60	6f	70.32	107–110	+29.61	0.53	4.19 (4.24)	6.51 (6.46)
7.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3-	0.60	6g	91.86	118–120	+230.50	0.36	4.21 (4.24)	6.43 (6.46)

Satisfactory C, H analysis was obtained for all the compounds.

isothiocyanate (0.005 *M*, 5.5 g) and aryl amines (0.005 *M*) in 35 ml benzene were refluxed over boiling water bath for about 3 h. Then the solvent was distilled off and the resulting syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a white granular solid, which was crystallized with chloroform-ether.

Synthesis of 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-4-aryl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (hydrochlorides) (3a-g) :

A mixture of phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) (0.005 *M*) and 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1a-g) (0.005 *M*) in chloroform was refluxed for 3 h. Then the solvent was distilled off and the resulting syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (3a-g) (Table 1). The products were crystallized from chloroform-petroleum ether.

Synthesis of 4-phenyl-5-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides) (6a) :

A chloroform solution of *N*-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (4) (1.86 g, 0.0025 *M* in 5 mL) was mixed with chloroform solution of 1,3-diphenyl thiocarbamide (5) (0.57 g, 0.0025 *M* in 25 mL). The mixture was shaken for few minutes and then refluxed over a boiling water bath for 3 h. The evolution of HCl was noticed. The solvent CHCl₃ was distilled off and the resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), when pale yellow solid was isolated 6a (2.142 g, 88.51 %). The solid was crystallized from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 122–126 °C.

3a : m.p. 132–135 °C; yield 80%, [α]²⁸_D +113° (c, 0.156 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) : 3066 (Ar-H stretching), 1728.8 (C=O), 1602.8 (C=N), 1270 (C–O), 765.8 (C–S), 854.4 (lactosyl C–H deformation), 709.2 cm⁻¹ (C–H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.14–7.07 (45H, m, aromatic protons), 5.91–5.73 (14H, m, lactosyl protons); Mass (*m/z*) : 1411 (M⁺), 1412 (M⁺+1), 1337 (M⁺-2HCl), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 67.28; H, 4.29; N, 3.12; S, 4.69. Calcd. for C₇₅H₅₉O₁₇N₃S₂ : C, 67.31; H, 4.41; N, 3.14; S, 4.78%).

3b : m.p. 155–158 °C; yield 82%, [α]²⁸_D + 95° (c, 0.156 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) : 3065 (Ar-H stretching), 1728.5 (C=O), 1607.4 (C=N), 1270.7 (C–O), 771.4 (C–8), 854.4 (lactosyl C–H deformation), 709.2 cm⁻¹ (C–H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.14–7.07 (44H, m, aromatic protons), 5.91–5.73 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 4.57–4.21 (3H, s, -CH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 1424 (M⁺), 1425 (M⁺+1), 1351 (M⁺-2HCl), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 67.18; H, 4.41; N, 3.12; S, 4.53. Calcd. for C₇₆H₆₁O₁₇N₃S₂ : C, 67.50; H, 4.51; N, 3.10; S, 4.73%).

3e : m.p. 146–148 °C; yield 90%, [α]²⁸_D + 118° (c, 0.156 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) : 3065 (Ar-H stretching), 1728.6 (C=O), 1627.4 (C=N), 1271.1 (C–O), 771.4 (C–S), 854.4 (lactosyl C–H deformation), 709.7 cm⁻¹ (C–H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.14–7.07 (44H, m, aromatic protons), 5.91–5.73 (14H, m, lactosyl protons); Mass (*m/z*) : 1447 (M⁺), 1448 (M⁺+1), 1372 (M⁺-2HCl), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-

$C_{12}H_{12}O_2$), 335 (TBG- $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$), 105 ($C_6H_5CO^+$); (Found : C, 65.38; H, 4.26; N, 3.01; S, 4.37. Calcd. for $C_{75}H_{58}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$: C, 65.59; H, 4.22; N, 3.06; S, 4.66%).

6a : IR (KBr) : 1750.8 (C=O), 1542.1 (C=N), 1275.2 (C-N), 1231.8 (C-O), 494.9 (C-S), 693.9 (mono substituted phenyl ring), characteristic of lactose at 1051.5 and 905.2 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.63–7.26 (10H, m, Ar-H), 5.35–3.77 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.18–1.96 (21H, acetyl protons); Mass (m/z) : 975 (M^+), 903, 888, 619, 559, 331, 227 (base peak), 169, 95 (Found : C, 49.19; H, 4.57; N, 4.25; S, 6.59. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{45}O_{17}N_3S_2 \cdot 2HCl$: C, 49.18; H, 4.85; N, 4.30; S, 6.56%).

6b : IR (KBr) : 3076.1 (Ar-H), 2937.5 (C-H aliphatic), 1743.0 (C=O), 1534.1 (C=N), 1374.2 (C-N), 1241.5 (C-O), characteristic of lactose at 1054.6 and 907.3, 754.6 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.82–7.21 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.40–3.70 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.25–1.96 (21H, acetyl protons); Mass (m/z) : 1009 (M^+), 937, 884, 808, 619, 331, 261 (base peak), 91 (Found : C, 47.08; H, 4.31; N, 4.11; S, 6.30. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{44}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl \cdot 2HCl$: C, 47.51; H, 4.58; N, 4.16; S, 6.34%).

6f : IR (KBr) : 2932.5 (C-H aliphatic), 1740.0 (C=O), 1537.9 (C=N), 1377.0 (C-N), 1244.7 (C-O), characteristic of lactose at 1053.6 and 904.6, 754.0 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR (ppm) : δ 7.60–7.12 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.35–3.75 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.51–1.96 (21H, acetyl protons), 1.25 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3); Mass (m/z) : 990 ($M+1$)⁺, 884, 677, 619, 331, 241 (base peak), 91 (Found : C, 49.62; H, 4.69; N, 4.19; S, 6.51. Calcd. for $C_{41}H_{47}O_{17}N_3S_2 \cdot 2HCl$: C, 49.70; H, 4.98; N, 4.24; S, 6.47%).

Antimicrobial activities :

All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup plate agar diffusion method by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent. Amikacin (100 $\mu g/ml$) was used as a standard for antibacterial activity and fluconazole (100 $\mu g/ml$) as a standard for antifungal activity. The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*,

Proteus vulgaris and *Salmonella typhi* in nutrient agar medium and for antifungal activity against *Rhizoctonia*, *Candida guilliermondii*, *A. niger* and *Microsporum* in potato dextrose agar medium.

It has been observed that all of these synthesized compounds showed nearly the same inhibitory activity as that of the standard Amikacin and Fluconazole. Similarly it has also been observed that some of these compounds exhibited interesting microbial activities. **3b**, **3d**, **3e**, **3g** and **6a** exhibited most significant activity against *Salmonella* and *E. coli* while **3f** and **6c** inhibited *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. All other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity.

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